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PROTECTION OF LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE AND PROBLEMS OF CANAL BANKS IN TASHKENT CITY

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This article talks about the city of Tashkent and the banks of the canals, which have gradually reached our time in the urban planning of our country. Guidelines for the use of landscape architecture and the use of ornamental and medicinal plants are provided.

Keywords: *Choch-tepa, Choch Ash-Shosh, Stone City, Chirchik river landscape, natural landscape, anthropogenic landscape, landscape architecture, landscape design, Introductory.*

First of all, let's look at the history of the city of Tashkent. A few centuries ago, in place of the city of Tashkent, the old Shosh-tepa was called Choch-tepa by its

second name. Its meaning is "6 hills". In the 8th century, Tashkent was supported by the Arabs, at that time it was called Choch, and a large city was reported. It is interesting to note that the name of the city was not used properly by the Arabs

because they do not have the sound "Ch" and changed it to Choch Ash-Shosh. In 819, a new city was built in the place of the city of Mahadina Ash Shosh, protected by the

emir of Yahya Ibn Asad. Later it was called Shoshkent, and after centuries Shoshkent became Tashkent, meaning "Stone City".

Every hundred years, Uzbekistan is slowly flourishing and joining the developed countries. In the Middle Ages, Tashkent was known as the Eastern Mud City. Since the Stone Age, people's desire to cultivate plants, beautiful nature, and use fertile land has been ingrained in our blood. There are many fertile soils that can be especially abundant. The Chirchik river joins the Syrdarya. Today, these canals look natural, but they were dug by humans 2,500 years ago for irrigation. As a result of this work, almost half of our Republic is covered by green areas. Direct and create 69m² of green plants. 45% increase in addition to what we achieved independently. Adilova L.A., Tokhtakhodjaeva M, who contributed to the development of the art of landscape architecture in Uzbekistan, Abdurazzakova VU etc. are historically connected. Isamuhamedova DU "Fundamentals of urban planning" study support, while supporting the world experience of urban planning development, Uzbekistan has preserved its own aspects of urban planning. In these books, the environment, nature, climate and landscape of our homeland Urban planning is widely revealed. Also, the basics of greening and landscape organization of cities are shown in educational support tools provided by Isomuhamedova DU, Sodikova MA, Kamilova XX, Talipov M.A. This area includes trees, creeping plants, grasses, ground cover plants that are very large and these plants are used for architectural small-scale decorative animal works. Any regular plancomposition is an excellent light for the light if it works by seeing the modern and positional changes of the living nature, because it is provided with the help of the environment. The main tasks of landscape architecture are natural and artificial elements of open spaces, beautification, planning of cities. But the research of canal areas of cities, their landscape organization, and their study are shown only in the form of some examples. Payments and research in this area are almost not carried out. Small recreation areas on the waterside of Tashkent city will be located on the restoration of more. Kalitsha, its modern appearance and equipment should be widely used, not forgetting our non-

coastal national traditions, which are planned to be built and renovated in our country . We also have canalside areas that have not been enhanced for landscaping and landscaping. An example In millet, we can take the big canal of Salar, which Mirzo placed in Ulug'bek district. The canal was used for several purposes in the early 1980s, its main purpose being irrigation. Its length is 60 km ² (from the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan). About Salar artificial channel. The company will organize a millennium. It starts from the Bozsuv canal, and its base is made of concrete. In recent years, the first cement concrete area is noticeable because it has decreased significantly and has become one of the most unsafe areas in the city. Due to the fact that the Salar canal in Tashkent city flows through a busy area and industrial enterprises, it collects a lot of waste. The sad thing is that the people living on the banks of the canal have built chicken houses, latrines, and manufacturing plants to create conditions for themselves, knowing the damage they cause to the environment and their health, and the wastes from them are flowing into the water. On June 25, 2018, Tashkent's canals were monitored by satellite, beautification and restoration, illegally occupied areas, and garbage dumps along the canals were cleaned. The mayor of the city, LLC, GUVU, Youth Union took part in inspecting the Salar canal. It consists of extracting clean drinking water under the city and creating an ecologically clean environment. Based on the existing conditions and

requirements in each city, guidelines for the organization of coastal areas are developed. Today, it is necessary to organize the coastal areas and find new strategies. The career of greening the coastal areas in the urban areas reveals the territorial and functional developments of the modern scenic recreation system of Tashkent city.

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